

Risk factors of becoming diabetics

Here are the possible causes of becoming diabetic:

- You are 35 years old or over.
- Your parents have diabetes.
- You are of Indian descent.
- You have given birth to a baby that weighed over 4kg at birth or have had gestational diabetes during pregnancy.
- You have high cholesterol or other fats in the blood.
- You have high blood pressure or heart disease.
- You are overweight.
- You do not exercise regularly.
- You do not eat healthily.

Analyze your own risk of becoming diabetic by de-tapping or tapping on each cause. You can check it yourself whether you have diabetes by consulting a health professional.

Diabetes

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...video of each cause plays and the manikin moves closer to diabetes...

Then the SASLI signs to prompt the user to select or deselect each video, which is now acting as a button.